

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

TƏHSİL KONTEKSTİNDƏ RƏQƏMSALLAŞMA

*Ramazanova G.
Azərbaycan Dövlət
Pedaqoji Universiteti*

DIGITALIZATION IN THE CONTEXT OF EDUCATION

*Ramazanova G.
Azerbaijan State
Pedagogical University*

Annotasiya

Məqalə təhsildə rəqəmsallaşmadan bəhs edir. Texnologiya əsrində, xüsusilə pandemiya dövründə və sonrasında tədris prosesinin təşkili məsələlərinə toxunulur.

Abstract

The article is about digitization in education. In the age of technology, especially during and after the pandemic, the issues of organizing the educational process are addressed.

Açar sözlər: rəqəmsallaşma, təhsil, texnologiya.

Keywords: digitalization, education, technology.

Today, digital competence is important and necessary for everyone in order to be able to actively and continuously participate in society at different levels (economic, social, cultural and educational) and to take advantage of the internet while building resilience to potential risks. The use of digital technologies for social and democratic participation requires the ability to engage positively, critically and competently in the digital environment. Skills are needed to access, select and interpret information, communicate effectively and create content in a way that respects human rights and dignity and uses technology responsibly.

How should we use digital technology in education?

All phases of education have a key role to play in enabling students to continuously acquire and develop the digital competences needed for life, work and learning. There are also concerns about children's socio-emotional, cognitive and physical development due to the potential excessive "screen time". Given that the effects of technology can depend on many factors, including the type of technology used and its purpose, evidence-based guidelines and effective practices are needed to encourage healthy and meaningful use of digital technology from an early age.

Digitalization can simply be explained as the transformation of the skills needed by the world's working population and the young in order to successfully engage in a globalized modern economy. In a learning environment, it is changing the way students learn and also the ways by which institutions deliver education (Webb, McQuaid & Webster, 2021). With the case of covid-19 pandemic, the education system in many countries faced problems as they needed to lead the lectures through digital technologies. But before pandemic digitalization was presented as a universal good but after it became a need and higher education institutions observed a need to provide digital platforms

to their students to minimize influence in their learning process. Higher education is one of those industries that should feel the need to assign infrastructure and provide digital technologies for education. Digital transformation alters the experience of the universities and universities need to understand the necessity of developing new situations [Efimov & V. Lapteva, 2018]. Nowadays, especially during and after the pandemic, digital technologies are used for study, work, and for leisure time and it is hard to imagine a life without digital technologies. Similarly, the education system is rapidly changing towards distance learning and cloud computing tools are examples of significant technologies responsible for online lecturing. Before we further dive into digitalization effects on student learning experiences, we must first look into what distance learning is. If we look at the past literature, distance learning can simply be explained as the efforts of providing access to learning for those who are geographically distant [Moore, Dickson Deane & Galyen, 2011]. This means that distance learning occurs when the resources are provided to students who may not be geographically or physically present at a university or institution. In our look for past literature, it was observed that researchers have used inconsistent definitions of distance learning and distance education. Moore, Dickson-Deane & Galyen (2002) in their research point out that as computers became more evolved, they became more involved in the delivery of education, which along with other electronic media were the first enablers of distance learning. Hence, distance learning (DL) can simply be explained as a mechanism in which learning resources and learning materials are made available for individuals which may not be physically or geographically at a university or higher education institution. Lastly, comes hybrid learning which is a result of both, face-to-face learning and distance learning hence the

name, hybrid learning (HL). The disruption in digitalization ultimately leads to changes in the students' mind-sets and along with the learning goals of higher education change. This means that there is a need to adjust and modify learning processes. Digital natives "have little patience for lectures, step-by-step logic, and "tell-test" instruction [Sedelmaier & Landes, 2019].

The first and foremost, benefit of various digitalized communication channels is that contents and knowledge becomes accessible and independent of time or place restrictions [Sedelmaier & Landes, 2019]. With the help of advanced internet search engines, students gain access to knowledge anywhere and at any time. With the help of IOT, cloud computing has been made possible which connects learning managing systems enabling them to share, distribute and retain information on a mass scale. Hence, as compared to previous years, learning processes have become more effective as they are supported by various digitalized technologies. Furthermore, education has also become more accessible to more people.

Teachers' positions in higher education have gone through enormous shifts in recent years and still, the question will remain if technology could replace teachers completely. Researchers mentioned that some teachers are very passionate and quick to learn new technologies and are open to developing their digital skills. Some lecturers see technology as a tool for teaching and learning and they are eager to learn the new technologies and add to their competencies [Teräs, Teräs, & Suoranta, 2022].

The negative side of digitalization in distance education is the challenge of managing the process of remote studies and lecturers and students in some cases

are not satisfied with distance learning. Sometimes students feel isolated due to the lack of communication, particularly with teachers, because they spend more time at home in front of a computer.

The traditional classes at the universities is one of the factors that teachers and mentors need to consider when they think about digitalization since studying at the university and social environment in education are significant factors in young people's lives.

References

1. Efimov, V., & V. Lapteva, A. (2018). The Future of Universities: Is Digitalization the Priority? *Journal of Siberian Federal University*.
2. Hanappi-Egger, E. (2020). What digitalisation means for universities. *European Foundation for Management Development*. pg. 62
3. Moore, J., Dickson-Deane, C., & Galyen, K. (2011). e-Learning, online learning, and distance learning environments: Are they the same?. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 14(2), 129-135. doi: 10.1016/j.iheduc.2010.10.001
4. Teräs, H., Teräs, M., & Suoranta, J. (2022). The life and times of university teachers in the era of digitalization: A tragedy. *LEARNING, MEDIA AND TECHNOLOGY*. pg. 63
5. Webb, A., McQuaid, R., & Webster, C. (2021). Moving learning online and the COVID-19 pandemic: a university response. *World Journal of Science, Technology and Sustainable Development*, 18(1), 1-19. doi: 10.1108/wjstsd-11-2020-0090